

PROTOCOL FOR TESTING OF THE EWS AMONG PREGNANT AND POSTPARTUM WOMEN, YOUNG CHILDREN AND HEALTH WORKERS

Deliverable 5.2

Protocol for testing of the EWS among pregnant and postpartum women, young children and health workers

HIGH HORIZONS – D5.2

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Author(s)	ULUND: Chuansi Gao, Clara Heil, Jakob Eggeling, Günter Alce CeSHHAR: Stanley Luchters, Fortunate Machingura, Lameck Kachena Wits RHI: Ijeoma Solarin, Matthew Chersich, Shobna Sawry WHO: Annie Portela LSHTM: Veronique Filippi, Isabelle Lange, Giulia Greco, Nasser Fardousi KI: Nathalie Roos
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Definitions

Term	Definition
Acceptability	In this protocol, acceptability is defined as the extent of users' satisfaction from the use of the early warning system ClimApp-MCH. Acceptability is the state or degree of being easily or conveniently done.
Early Warning System (EWS)	According to UN Climate Change Adaptation, an early warning system is an adaptive measure for climate change, using integrated communication systems to help communities prepare for hazardous climate-related events. A successful EWS saves lives and jobs, land and infrastructures and supports long-term sustainability. In this protocol, the heat-health warning system is developed as a mobile phone application (ClimApp-MCH) including messages provided to maternal and child healthcare users to take actions to reduce heat-health risks. For users who do not have a mobile phone or are illiterate, the messages will be communicated through health workers.
Effectiveness	In the context of the ClimApp-MCH app, effectiveness is defined as the ability of the ClimApp-MCH to change knowledge/awareness of heat-health risks, and the ability to potentially have effects on biological outcomes and/or health outcomes of ClimApp-MCH users.
Feasibility	In this protocol, feasibility is defined as the capability of applying and using the ClimApp-MCH in these settings, and to get heat-health risk warnings and recommendations to the target populations.
Heat-Health Warning Systems (HHWS)	Heat-Health Warning Systems use climate and weather forecasts and pre-determined trigger levels of heat stress to provide advice to the public and initiate public health interventions designed to reduce health risks before, during, and after periods of extreme heat (WMO/WHO and GHHIN 2022). Another definition explains that a HHWS is designed to alert decision-makers and the general public to impending dangerous hot weather and to serve as a source of advice on avoiding negative health outcomes associated with hot weather (WHO/WMO 2015).
Heat stress	In this protocol, heat stress is defined as the net heat load to which a person is exposed from the combined contributions of thermal environmental factors (air temperature, humidity, air velocity, and radiant temperature), metabolic heat (the higher physical activity, more internal metabolic heat the body produces), and clothing worn (insulation and evaporative resistance hinder heat dissipation from the body) which results in an increase in heat storage in the body (adopted and modified from NIOSH 2016). Heat stress causes heat strain, i.e., thermal physiological responses such as increased heart rate, elevated body core temperature (hyperthermia), sweating, dehydration. Heat stress can further result in heat-related symptoms and illnesses such as dizziness, heat rashes, heat cramp, heat syncope, heat exhaustion, heat stroke and death.

Term	Definition
Usability	<p>Usability refers the extent to which a system, product or service can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use (ISO-9241-11:2018), where effectiveness is defined as accuracy and completeness with which users achieve specified goals; efficiency is defined as resources (time, human effort, costs and materials) used in relation to the results achieved; and satisfaction is defined as the extent to which the user's physical, cognitive and emotional responses that result from the use of a system, product or service meet the user's needs and expectations. Usability is crucial for the effective and accurate delivery of heat-health risk warnings to its users and the dissemination of messages to take necessary actions. This ensures the prevention and protection of users from heat-related risks, mitigating potential adverse health consequences.</p>

Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
ADH	Antidiuretic hormone
AIDS	Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome
ANC	Antenatal care
AT	Apparent Temperature
CHW	Community Health Worker
ClimApp-MCH	ClimApp for maternal and child health
COPD	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
CS	Clinical services
CSV	Comma separated values
EU	European Union
EWS	Early Warning System
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HHWS	Heat-Health Warning System
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996
HIV	Human immunodeficiency virus
HMIS	Health Management Information Systems
IDI	In-depth interviews
IM	Intervention Mapping
MNCH	Maternal, Neonatal, and Child Health
NCD	Noncommunicable diseases
PHC	Primary Healthcare
PHS	Public Health Services
PIS	Participant information sheet
PNC	Postnatal care
POPIA	Protection of Personal Information Act
PSSUQ	Post-Study System Usability Questionnaire
QoC	Quality of care
SA	South Africa
SUS	System Usability Scale
TB	Tuberculosis
UK	United Kingdom
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work package

Executive summary

The frequency and intensity of temperature extremes, and heatwaves have increased in the past four decades and are projected to continue rising. Accumulating evidence shows strong links to adverse human health outcomes because of heat exposure. Infants, children, pregnant women, the elderly, and manual and outdoor workers are most vulnerable. Heat-Health Warning Systems have the potential to act as crucial intervention gateways for providing individualized protection. However, the current state of Early Warning Systems (EWS) does not target maternal, newborn or child vulnerable groups, lacks sensitivity, primarily focusing on air temperature exposures and failing to address pertinent factors such as other thermal climate factors and individual circumstances. Moreover, the existing early warning systems often lack locally relevant messaging that is co-designed with the communities they serve.

HIGH Horizons employs a participatory approach to integrate several thermal climate and individual factors to develop locally-appropriate and culturally-sensitive messages, as part of the EWS. The developed smartphone-based EWS application (ClimApp-MCH) will be evaluated for its usability, acceptability and effectiveness in various contexts in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe, and among pregnant women, postpartum women and their children, and among health workers. Quantitative and qualitative research methods will be used in four prospective before-after cohorts. The study will be implemented by our in-country partners as follows:

Name of institution	Country	Address
Centre for Sexual Health & HIV & AIDS Research (CeSHHAR)	Zimbabwe	4 Bath Road, Belgravia, Harare, Zimbabwe
Climate and Health Directorate, Wits RHI, University of the Witwatersrand	South Africa	22 Esselen Street, Hillbrow Health Precinct, Hillbrow, 2001
Karolinska Institutet	Sweden	Department of Medicine, Solna, 17177, Stockholm, Sweden

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this document

This deliverable 5.2 describes the evaluation protocol of the ClimApp-MCH for maternal and child health, which is a personalized heat-health warning system (HHWS). The evaluation will take place in Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe among pregnant women, postpartum women and their children, and health workers. The ClimApp-MCH as an intervention tool is currently being developed under a separate deliverables, and this will not be described here. Here, we focus on the evaluation protocol.

1.2 Deviations from the original application

After discussions with the Steering Committee and the Scientific Advisory Board, we have opted for enrolling women in three separate cohorts with 6 months follow-up duration, instead of one cohort with 18 months duration. The total number of women enrolled will remain the same at 200 women per country. The revised approach allows the research team to have in-depth information about ClimApp-MCH use during hotter seasons in each of the critical periods: pregnancy, first 6-months postpartum during exclusive breastfeeding, and between 6-12 months postnatal with mixed infant feeding patterns. With 18-month follow-up there is always colder seasons involved. Moreover, shorter follow-up will ensure better cohort retention, and will allow for all required data to be obtained in a shorter period, which is beneficial given some delays against the planned timelines. The cohort with 20 health workers remains unchanged.

We have opted for adding assessment of heat-related biological markers (urine) to assess potential effect of the ClimApp-MCH. The rationale behind this selection comes from evidence and discussions with other biomarkers studies (including the biomarker study by our HIGH Horizons partner, University of Thessaly – see deliverable 2.12), although limited evidence exists about the best biomarker for

measuring heat-health impact. Dehydration as a consequence of heat exposure has been suggested as a cause of preterm birth. The potential mechanism includes i) reduction in uterine blood flow that can trigger prostaglandin release, ii) the release of antidiuretic hormone (ADH, a hormone engaged in water retention to stave against dehydration), and iii) excessive sweating and insufficient hydration in hot and humid environments or intensive physical work. This will now be measured at two timepoints during follow-up.

2 Background and study rationale

The frequency and intensity of temperature extremes, and heatwaves have increased in the past four decades and are projected to continue rising (Copernicus 2024, WMO 2023 State of Climate Services: Health, IPCC Working Group II 2023, Burkart et al. 2021). Accumulating evidence shows strong links to adverse human health outcomes because of heat exposure. Infants, children, pregnant women, the elderly, manual and outdoor and health workers are vulnerable (WMO 2023 State of Climate Services: Health, IPCC Working Group II 2023, Burkart et al. 2021).

A heat-health Early Warning System (EWS) has the potential to act as a crucial intervention gateway for providing individualized protection and plays a pivotal role in the health sector's response to heat waves, across the world (WMO & WHO 2015). However, at present EWS does not target pregnant women and children as vulnerable groups, and lacks sensitivity, primarily focusing only on environmental air temperature exposures and failing to address other pertinent factors such as individual circumstances and other thermal climate factors such as humidity and radiant temperature. Moreover, the existing EWS often lacks locally relevant messaging that is co-designed with the communities they serve.

The existing EWSs work for the public when weather forecasts predict that a pre-specified air temperature threshold is likely to be exceeded, warnings are issued, and a series of tiered interventions are triggered. Current generic EWS lacks consideration of the specific vulnerabilities of pregnant and postpartum women, newborns and children with considerable health implications. Many EWS still have heat stress cut-off thresholds directed to the entire population, and do not adequately stratify warnings by level of vulnerability of distinct groups. Basing threshold cutoffs on general predictive modelling of air temperature-mortality relationships provides only crude estimates of mortality risks, thereby giving warnings too late. Moreover, advice that accompanies warnings is also often generic, rather than tailored to locally available resources and protective practices. Lastly, the potential for smartphone and artificial intelligence to drive an EWS has not been fully exploited to date, particularly for pregnant and postpartum women, infants and children. There needs to be more focus on making people aware of the negative health risks of the heat.

The HIGH Horizons teams will employ a participatory approach to develop locally appropriate and culturally sensitive messages, as part of the development of the ClimApp-MCH application, based on ClimApp (deliverable 3.5). ClimApp is a smartphone app that integrates comprehensive heat stress indices and individual factors to provide a personalized tool to provide heat stress warning and advice when facing extreme heat events. The current version of ClimApp is being adapted to vulnerable groups of pregnant and postpartum women and their children. ClimApp could play a role as a tool to make heat warnings more accessible for everyone and make people aware of appropriate behaviour during periods with high ambient temperatures (Folkerts et al 2021, Eggeling et al 2022).

The ClimApp-MCH will assess the heat-health risk and facilitate heat stress reduction for pregnant and post-partum women, infants as well as health workers, particularly those health workers whose work environments are not cooled in hot

season. It will be implemented in three countries: South Africa, Sweden, and Zimbabwe. As the three countries differ in climate, culture, and socio-economic contexts, ClimApp-MCH and its respective evaluation need to take these factors into account. Moreover, the EWS will be evaluated in both rural (Zimbabwe) and urban settings (South Africa and Sweden). South Africa and Zimbabwe share a more similar climate, compared to Sweden, and are countries where extreme heat is expected to cause detrimental effects for maternal and perinatal health including pre-term births, stillbirths, low birth weight newborns and other adverse outcomes (Burkart et al. 2021). Since the average literacy levels (including digital literacy) in South Africa and Zimbabwe are lower compared to Sweden, the intervention requires further refinement of the EWS approach in order to address heat stress in a desired manner. While relying on technologies may be suitable in Sweden, a combination of technologies and warnings communicated by experienced health workers may be more advantageous in South Africa and Zimbabwe due to lower literacy rate.

The ClimApp-MCH thus needs to be evaluated for its feasibility, usability, and acceptability in these various contexts. The findings will be crucial for improving ClimApp-MCH and for contributing to protecting the maternal and infant health situation from increasing temperatures in these targeted regions.

3 Intervention using ClimApp-MCH

According to UN Climate Change Adaptation, an Early Warning System is an adaptive measure for climate change, using integrated communication systems to help communities prepare for hazardous climate-related events. A successful EWS saves lives and jobs, land and infrastructures and supports long-term sustainability. EWSs will assist public officials and administrators in their planning, saving money in the long run and protecting economies (<https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/climate-solutions/early-warning-systems>).

The key concept of the EWS in this project is a mobile phone app that is under development (deliverable 3.3). The ClimApp-MCH is building on a previously developed app, named ClimApp, which was not specific to vulnerable groups such as the pregnant women and children, but available for a wider population. In a field test in the heat, 134 participants filled in the required personal settings into the app and indicated if the estimated thermal strain by ClimApp matched their thermal perception. A total of 45 of the participants filled in a user satisfaction questionnaire. Results show that ClimApp is able to predict the heat strain of the user but may underestimate perceived heat strain. Furthermore, participants were positive about the user-friendliness of ClimApp. The study also shows that there needs to be more focus on making people aware of the negative health risks of heat.

The app makes use of local weather forecasts and integrates human thermal stress models to predict thermal stress, where heat stress and its respective influence on maternal and child health is the focus in this project.

The ClimApp-MCH provides heat stress warnings based on a combination of local weather conditions and individual vulnerability/risk factors, for example age, BMI before pregnancy, gestational age. When the heat level determined by the integrated heat stress index exceeds the threshold, a warning is triggered, and the user is notified of the heat-health risks. The user is then recommended with a relevant set of locally-adapted messages/advice on preventive and protective actions she can take to reduce heat risks.

These messages will either be delivered through the App or communicated face-to-face by community health workers. The app may be provided directly to the participant when literacy and smartphone penetration is high, but a more community-based approach is required when the literacy and smartphone penetration is low. The literacy rate for individuals aged 15 and above stands at 90% in both South Africa and Zimbabwe while in Sweden it is 99%. Mobile phone

penetration is high in South Africa. Approximately 96% of urban households have a mobile phone (DHS) and smartphone coverage is estimated to be 91.2% (ICASA, 2020). In addition, urban areas of Gauteng province, where the study site is located, have 100% 4G coverage. We therefore anticipate that most women in the area will have access to a smartphone. On the contrary, in the Zimbabwe rural study site, mobile phone network coverage is limited and limits phone penetration. We are therefore exploring a different model of 'health-health warning delivery' in this context as part of the 'message development' deliverable (deliverable 3.5). The app is designed to deliver warnings and advice to the user. When the app is not used by the participant, a health worker may deliver these warnings and advice in a suitable manner.

Appropriate use of the ClimApp-MCH may prevent heat strain by adopting adaptive behaviours. At a minimum, we expect the ClimApp-MCH to increase awareness and knowledge about heat risks. With increased knowledge, the risk of heat stress may be reduced as the person may take proper action to prepare for and reduce harmful exposure. Adaptive behaviours are context-specific and are being co-developed under a separate deliverable (see deliverable 3.6).

The mother can use the infant profile (one of the four user profiles) in the ClimApp-MCH to receive relevant heat risk warnings and messages/advice triggered and designed to protect the infant during heat events. The mother is recommended to take actions according to the advice to support infant health.

ClimApp-MCH will be used as an intervention tool, but also as a means of testing its validity and perceived health benefits, e.g., raising awareness of appropriate behaviour during periods with high extreme heat. Women would use the App during pregnancy, and complete thermal perception data, acceptability and usability questions and user history on the app.

4 Aim and objectives

The overall aim of the study is to assess the operational performance of the ClimApp-MCH and to achieve knowledge change concerning heat-health risks in three diverse settings: Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

More specifically, the **primary objective** is to assess the feasibility, acceptability and usability of the newly developed ClimApp-MCH app among pregnant women, postpartum women (for both themselves and their infants up to 12 months), and health workers. We will assess the ClimApp-MCH in its entirety, including the app itself as well as the messages sent through the app.

Secondary objectives are:

- 1) To assess the uptake of the ClimApp-MCH when used by pregnant women, postpartum women/mothers, and health workers;
- 2) To assess the effectiveness and perceived impact of the ClimApp-MCH on knowledge of pregnant women, postpartum women/mothers, and health workers;
- 3) To explore the use of urine biomarkers for measuring intervention effectiveness among pregnant women, postpartum women/mothers, children and health workers;
- 4) To assess the economic burden associated with heat exposure among pregnant women;
- 5) To assess the cost-consequence of the adaptation and distribution of the ClimApp-MCH for use in pregnant women.

5 Methodology

5.1 Study design

We will implement a before-after intervention cohort design with a six-month follow-up period, to achieve the stated implementation research objectives. The study will enrol and follow four (4) prospective cohorts of participants in each country (Sweden, South Africa and Zimbabwe) for a duration of six months. Key study visits will occur at the time of enrolment, with subsequent follow-up visits after two and six months. We anticipate that study follow-up of women during pregnancy, and mothers and infants, and health workers will overlap with the warmer season(s) in each of the respective countries. We will employ mixed-methods research incorporating both qualitative (focus group discussions and in-depth interviews) and quantitative approaches (questionnaire administration, in-app features of data collection, and biomarkers).

The design is appropriate as the study will focus primarily on thermal perception data, acceptability, and usability of ClimApp-MCH by pregnant women and mothers with infants up to 1 year of age, and health workers. A large-scale comparative trial is felt not to be appropriate at this early stage of EWS development.

5.2 Study sites

This study will be conducted across three distinct climate settings (Sweden, South Africa, and Zimbabwe).

In South Africa, the participants will be recruited from a health facility which is located East of Pretoria in Gauteng Province. The facility offers a range of primary health services including low risk maternity services where every month, health workers attend to approximately 250 women for a first antenatal care visit and approximately 74 births. There are 82 health workers employed in the antenatal and delivery units made up of 77 professional nurses and 5 doctors.

The participants in Zimbabwe will be recruited from a district hospital and its surrounding community. Women will be recruited from antenatal services, or through community health volunteers, who are active in the region. The district hospital has an average annual number of 2,295 births done by 38 midwives and 84 registered general nurses.

Recruitment in Sweden will occur within the greater Stockholm area, involving 15 antenatal clinics. Each clinic is staffed by approximately six midwives.

5.3 Study population

The study population comprises pregnant and postpartum women, their infants up to 12 months of age and health workers who provide maternity care (antenatal, childbirth and postnatal). To ensure diversity of participants, four different cohorts will be enrolled in each country, and all followed for a duration of six months. More specifically, the inclusion criteria for each country are listed below (Table 1). No additional exclusion criteria will be applied to ensure a better understanding of feasibility, acceptability and usability among a diverse group of women, children and health workers.

In each country, the following cohort sizes are expected:

- Cohort 1: 100 pregnant women per country (total n=300)
- Cohort 2: 50 women with a live-birth infant in the past three months per country (total n=150)
- Cohort 3: 50 women with a child aged 6-9 months of age (total n=150)
- Cohort 4: 20 health workers (total n=60).

Table 1. Inclusion criteria for the four cohorts, by country

	Country		
	South Africa	Sweden	Zimbabwe
Cohort 1 (n=100)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Women who are confirmed pregnant, and in second trimester of pregnancy as assessed by a registered health worker ii. Aged 18 years and older iii. Attending antenatal care services at one the participating health facilities iv. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app v. Intending to remain in the study area for the next six (6) months vi. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Women who are confirmed pregnant, and in second trimester of pregnancy as assessed by a registered health worker ii. Aged 18 years and older iii. Swedish born and migrant population iv. Recruited from the participating health facility (ANC services at KUH) v. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app vi. Intending to remain in the study area for the next six months vii. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Women who are confirmed pregnant, and in second trimester of pregnancy as assessed by a registered health worker ii. Aged 16 years and older iii. Attending antenatal care services at one the participating health facilities, or identified in the community by a community health worker iv. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app v. Intending to remain in the study area for the next six (6) months vi. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation
Cohort 2 (n=50):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Women with a live-birth infant in the past three (3) months ii. Aged 18 years and older iii. Recruited from the participating health facilities (e.g. postnatal care services) iv. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app v. Intending to remain in the study area for the next six (6) months vi. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Women with a live-birth infant in the past three (3) months ii. Aged 18 years and older iii. Recruited from the participating health facility (e.g. postnatal care services at KUH) iv. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app v. Intending to remain in the study area for the next six months vi. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Women with a live-birth infant in the past three (3) months ii. Aged 16 years and older iii. Recruited from the participating health facilities (e.g. postnatal care services), or identified in the community by a community health worker iv. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app v. Intending to remain in the study area for the next six (6) months vi. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation

	Country		
	South Africa	Sweden	Zimbabwe
Cohort 3 (n=50):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Women with a child aged 6-9 months of age ii. Aged 18 years and older iii. Recruited from the participating health facilities (e.g. postnatal care services) iv. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app v. Intending to remain in the study area for the next six (6) months vi. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Women with a child aged 6-9 months of age ii. Aged 18 years and older iii. Recruited from the participating health facility (e.g. postnatal care services at KUH) iv. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app v. Intending to remain in the study area for the next six (6) months vi. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Women with a child aged 6-9 months of age ii. Aged 16 years and older iii. Recruited from the participating health facilities (e.g. postnatal care services), or identified in the community by a community health worker iv. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app v. Intending to remain in the study area for the next six (6) months vi. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation
Cohort 4 (n=20):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Registered health worker in the country of operation ii. Aged 18 years and older iii. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app iv. Employed at the participating health facility v. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Registered midwife in the country of operation ii. Aged 18 years and older iii. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app iv. Employed at the participating health facility v. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Registered health worker in the country of operation ii. Aged 18 years and older iii. Owns a smart phone which can run the ClimApp-MCH app iv. Employed at the participating health facility, either as a nurse, nurse-midwife or community health worker v. Able and willing to provide written informed consent for study participation

For the qualitative inquiries, participants will be recruited with the same inclusion/exclusion criteria as stipulated above for the four cohorts. Participants in the qualitative inquiries may, or may not, also participate in the focus group discussions.

6 Study components

6.1 Study screening

For the cohorts, we will screen potentially eligible participants consecutively at the respective sites. Screening processes will assess the main eligibility criteria as stipulated for each cohort.

For the qualitative components, participants will be purposively selected based on the expectation that likely rich perspectives will be obtained.

Recruitment is not competitive between the countries. Underperformance of recruitment from any of the three country sites will mean a longer recruitment period. If enrolment targets cannot be achieved, this will be discussed with the HIGH Horizons Steering Committee (senior members from each partner), and local stakeholders/service providers, and mitigation measures planned.

6.2 Study enrolment

Those eligible and interested to participate, and meeting the eligibility criteria, will undergo the consenting process. The information about the study will be presented and explained to the potential participants, giving them time to read the information sheet and consent form. Potential participants will have had the opportunity to have any of their questions answered. Potential participants will sign the consent form, retaining a copy for themselves. A research assistant will be present to help sign and verify informed consent forms. A suitable venue, ensuring privacy and convenience for participants, such as a community centre, local school, or health facility, will be selected for the qualitative inquiries. Snacks and beverages will be provided, and participants will be reimbursed for transportation costs.

Once written informed consent is obtained, and participants formally enrolled into the study, study visit procedures will be administered as per the below schedule.

6.3 Enrolment visit

The timing of enrolments are scheduled separately in each country to ensure adequate follow-up during the hotter seasons, see Gantt chart for more details.

At the enrolment visit, the following procedures will be conducted:

➤ **Administration of the baseline questionnaire**

(pre-use of the ClimApp-MCH; see further details in chapter on 'data collection and study measures' below)

- a) Socio-demographic and economic characteristics
- b) Obstetric history
- c) Medical history, and history of heat related illnesses
- d) Child health information and nurturing behaviours (if applicable)
- e) Wellbeing
- f) Daily activities
- g) Household expenditure and economic burden
- h) Knowledge and behaviours of heat risks
- i) Heat related responses and illnesses in the past week
- j) Experience of using mobile phone and app

➤ **Medical examination**

Height and weight will be measured for all cohort participants.

➤ **Urine sampling**

A urine midstream sample will be obtained for assessment of urine specific gravity and urine osmolality (see further details below).

➤ **Training session**

Following these enrolment study procedures, participants will be invited to take part in a 30-minute training session where the ClimApp-MCH app is installed on their personal phones, and potential personal vulnerabilities

are input into the App (including for their babies when applicable) such as age, body weight before pregnancy, body height.

6.4 Follow-up visit 1

During the first follow-up visit, which occurs two months after enrolment, the following procedures will be conducted:

➤ Follow-up questionnaire

- a) Changes to socio-demographic and economic characteristics
- b) Changes to daily activities
- c) Medical events since last visit (pregnant woman/mother and baby)
- d) Household expenditure and economic burden
- e) Wellbeing
- f) Child health information and nurturing behaviours (if applicable)
- g) Knowledge and behaviours of heat risks
- h) Heat related responses and illnesses since last visit and in the past week
- i) ClimApp-MCH feasibility, acceptability and usability assessment

➤ Urine sampling

A urine midstream sample will be obtained for assessment of urine specific gravity and urine osmolality (see further details below).

6.5 Follow-up visit 2

Six months after the enrolment and the use of the ClimApp-MCH in the hot season, the participants will be visited again (endline visit). This visit will be at the end of the hot season.

➤ Endline questionnaire

- a) Changes to socio-demographic and economic characteristics
- b) Changes to daily activities
- c) Medical events since last visit (pregnant woman/mother and baby)

- d) Household expenditure and economic burden
- e) Wellbeing
- f) Child health information and nurturing behaviours (if applicable)
- g) Knowledge and behaviours of heat risks
- h) Heat related responses and illnesses since last visit and in the past week
- i) ClimApp-MCH feasibility, acceptability and usability assessment.

➤ **Urine sampling**

A urine midstream sample will be obtained for assessment of urine specific gravity and urine osmolality (see further details below).

6.6 Additional participant contact

In the hot season, during periods of increased heat (e.g. higher temperatures, heat wave), and when ClimApp-MCH triggers a high level of heat risk warning, participants will be contacted via their phones, e.g. through automatic notifications, to complete the short App-based or web-based questionnaire (heat perception, thermal comfort, child care practices e.g., breastfeeding) and submit heat and response data using the integrated Research Function (user's feedback system) in the App.

7 Data collection and study measures

7.1 Quantitative data collection using semi-structured questionnaires

Semi-structured questionnaires will be administered to collect quantitative data from participants at enrolment, and again after two and six months. Questionnaires cover various aspects such as participant's socio-demographic characteristics, employment history, medical history, general wellbeing, knowledge of heat risks, knowledge and experience with heat warnings, heat-

related symptoms and illnesses, and economic burden. In addition, feasibility, acceptability and usability of the ClimApp-MCH will be assessed at follow up visits, after participants have had an opportunity to engage with the app. Variables to assess the pilot-effectiveness include the level of awareness, knowledge of heat risks, perceived changes of behaviour, and the biological markers (Urine specific gravity (USG) and urine osmolality; see chapter below). Table 2 describes the variables of interest in more detail.

Table 2. Details of the quantitative data collection

Thematic categories in questionnaire	Details on variables to be collected and constructs
Socio-demographic and economic characteristics	Socio-demographic information and socio-economic status information, including age, employment, education level, marital status, ethnicity, migration, type of accommodation, building structure, access to green space, size of household
Obstetric history	This includes pregnancy-related and/or post-partum-related information if applicable, e.g. complications, gestational age, twin or singleton birth, (expected) date of delivery, caesarean section, use of healthcare services for herself or her newborn)
Medical history	Medical history, and history of heat related illnesses
Wellbeing	A validated general and mental health questionnaire will be used, including assessment of 'mental self-rated wellbeing'.
Daily activities	We will collect information on daily activities, including professional and personal daily activities and the location of these activities (e.g. whether at home or somewhere else)
Child health information and nurturing behaviours	Child health information and nurturing behaviours include information on (exclusive) breastfeeding and infant feeding practices (for postpartum women only), and access to help with childcare
Heat related responses and illnesses	This information includes thermal perception of heat (ISO PMV rating scale), thermal comfort, skin wetness sensation, heat related symptoms (headache, dizziness), thirst sensation, urine colour, muscle cramp, heat syncope, heat exhaustion, heat stroke.
Knowledge and behaviours of heat risks	Knowledge and behaviour related to ambient heat impacts on health includes questions on what they know/understand about heat-health risks and how they would reduce potential heat risks by behavioural measures/actions based on a case (a heat scenario) describing heat stress risks (see Annex II). The initial (pre EWS use) and final (post EWS use) survey will also include a heat stress case (Annex II) where the participant will be asked to plan actions/measures to reduce heat stress before and after the use of the ClimApp-MCH to compare if the users can take heat actions (behavioural changes) based on the EWS messages. Awareness and knowledge about heat stress, related health risks and preventive measures will also be evaluated before and after the use of the EWS app. For example, what the body responses can be in the

Thematic categories in questionnaire	Details on variables to be collected and constructs
	heat, how to identify dehydration, and how to cope with heat, can be presented to the user through the app.
Household expenditure and economic burden	We will assess both general and health-related data and opportunity costs (productivity foregone due to ill-health or heat). Questions in this section also aim to estimate the economic burden associated with heat exposure among pregnant women. We will examine whether those exposed to heat incur higher levels of household catastrophic payments for healthcare (health expenditures exceeding a given threshold of total non-food related household expenditure, e.g. 25%) and impoverishment effects of health expenditures (where non-poor households are pushed below the poverty line by health expenditures), and whether there are differential effects by socio-economic groups across sites. To estimate the economic burden, the survey will collect data on directly incurred expenditures associated with heat related-illness, general household expenditure and ownership of assets, and opportunity costs (cost of lost productivity due to heat-related morbidity).
ClimApp-MCH feasibility, acceptability and usability assessment	Feasibility and usability of the ClimApp-MCH is assessed by examining statistics on uptake of the app, frequency and patterns of use. Feedback and heat related health responses from the users and corresponding actual heat exposure will be collected through the app's 'research functionality'. The usability questions will only be included in the follow up and endline visits after participants have had some experience of using the App. This section of the questionnaire will include questions regarding usability according to System Usability Scale SUS (Annex I) or Post-Study System Usability Questionnaire PSSUQ (Annex I) to measure the ease of use and users' perceived satisfaction.

7.2 Biological markers of heat stress

Our consortium partner, University of Thessaly (UTH), conducts an in-depth biomarker study in a birth cohort of 500 pregnant women/child pairs in Greece (not described here). The overall aim of the biomarker study is to investigate the biological and physiological effects of heat exposure on pregnant women, fetuses, and newborns and to provide insights into the potential mechanisms governing the impacts of heat related exposures on maternal and child health. Much remains unknown on the most appropriate biomarker for assessing the effect of heat adaptation interventions such as the ClimApp-MCH.

In this protocol, and informed by the more in-depth HIGH Horizons biomarker study in Greece, participants enrolled in the cohorts in South Africa and Zimbabwe

will be requested to provide a urine sample at each study visit (enrolment, month 2 and month 6) for assessment of urine osmolality and urine specific gravity (USG). Although no formal sample size calculation will be performed, these urine biomarkers will be explored as potential intervention effectiveness markers, and compared to comprehensive biomarker data collected in Greece.

The rationale behind this selection comes from evidence and discussions with other biomarkers studies. Dehydration, as a consequence of heat exposure, has been suggested as a cause of preterm birth. The potential mechanism includes i) reduction in uterine blood flow that can trigger prostaglandin release, and ii) the release of antidiuretic hormone (ADH, a hormone engaged in water retention to stave against dehydration), iii) excessive sweating and insufficient hydration in hot and humid environments or intensive physical work.

Retention time of specimens depends on the decision to store in the two countries or to ship the samples to Greece for analysis, and will be determined later.

7.3 Focus group discussions

Focus group discussions (FGDs) with selected participants will allow for more in-depth exploration and feedback than the semi-structured questionnaire. Focus group discussions are small group discussions (6-12 participants) facilitated by two facilitators (generally one to lead the questions and discussion (moderator), and the other to observe and document the dynamics in the group (notetaker). In forming the groups, care is taken to ensure that the constellation of participants is one that allows them to speak openly and comfortably, and that notable power imbalances or hierarchies amongst the participants are minimized. The discussion is steered by the facilitator in such a way that encourages an exchange to take place amongst participants, allowing for further reactions and opinions to be expressed that might not otherwise emerge in the 1-to-1 researcher-interviewer format (see in-depth interviews below).

In each of the three countries, researchers will conduct 1-2 FGDs with participants as described for each of the four cohorts (pregnant/post-partum women and health workers, see cohort section). Each FGD will be comprised of 6-12 participants. FGDs will take place after participants have engaged with the ClimApp-MCH for at least two months to ensure that participants have had adequate experience using the ClimApp-MCH.

All FGDs will be facilitated by a social science researcher trained to use an open-ended, flexible topic guide that structures discussions to promote free-flowing dialogue and allows for the emergence of unexpected themes. The discussion will be conducted in the participants' language of choice and audio-recorded with their consent. The research assistant will take notes on participant dynamics and document details not captured in the recording.

Questions posed in the FGD will focus on participants' experience of using the ClimApp-MCH and explore if there have been any changes in either their perception of heat stress or changes in their actions/behaviours, or any impact on their productivity since using the EWS. Participants will also be invited to make recommendations on how the App could be improved. The draft FGD guide is contained in Annex III and the questions may be amended or refined for each country and also based on feedback from the follow-up visits.

The recording of the FGDs will be transcribed verbatim, and quality checked by the facilitators of the event who will add any additional information from observations for clarity and detail.

The information obtained in the focus group discussions is anonymous and will not be used and linked to individual participants in any reports and publications. Detailed instructions and procedures to conduct the focus group discussions will be adapted to local settings in each of the three countries.

7.4 In-depth interviews

Although the proposed method for qualitative data collection is through FGDs, countries have the flexibility to opt for telephonic interviews or in-depth face to face discussions when they come back for healthcare if deemed more practical. In the event of using telephonic interviews, the interview guide will closely align with the questions outlined in the FGD guide. This approach may become more appropriate if fewer number of participants can be identified (e.g. with health workers), or when more sensitive perspectives need to be shared.

8 Data management and analysis

8.1 Study data management

REDCap software will be used to manage the majority of quantitative data (semi-structured questionnaires and biological sample results) and offers an easy-to-use and secure method of flexible yet robust data collection that meets HIPAA compliance standards. It is a secure web application for building and managing online surveys and databases. This software is not open-source software, and it will be installed on a local web server.

The use of the ClimApp-MCH by the participant is recorded on the app server in Denmark. When the participant agrees to submit heat related responses through Research function of the app, the heat exposure and response data will be collected and stored on the server. These data on the server will be used for the assessment of feasibility and usability of the ClimApp-MCH, the analysis of heat exposure and response relationship, etc.

Data management will be carried out in accordance with the HIGH Horizons 'Data Management Plan' developed for the EU and dated 30 November 2022. The data management will also meet requirements specific to each country such as the Protection of Personal Information Act South Africa, or the Data Protection Act in

Zimbabwe. In accordance with this plan, our data management has the following characteristics, which is common to all study components, unless stated otherwise:

- Each participant will have a unique participant identification number. All hard copies of patient identifying data will be stored in a locked cabinet and electronic versions of transcripts will be stored on a secure SharePoint site on institutional servers, which are secure and protected by two-level authentication.
- Data will be fully anonymised or pseudonymised when sharing the data for analysis and when reporting of the research findings, for example, when participant quotes are used.
- When storing a copy of the data on local machines is required (e.g., for qualitative analysis), the data will be password protected and de-identified.
- Access to data will be restricted to a limited number of study staff that have appropriate training to manage data.
- Data storage will be protected against disaster and risk in compliance with the ISO/IEC 27001:2005 standards.
- When sharing data with the transcribers, they will not be sent by email but transferred safely using encryption or secure tools like Filesender.
- Data transfer between the High Horizons research sites and the broader High Horizons research team will only include de-identified data and will be conducted using secure, encrypted channels.
- Many scientific journals now expect that datasets from the study being reported on are made accessible to readers, and some mandate this as a condition of publication. Access to the data collected in this study will be partly restricted - i.e., the dataset will be shared only upon written application to the country-specific Principal Investigator (i.e. in-country scientific research coordinator) of this study. We will take actions to limit the restrictions, however, i.e., to have our datasets "as open as possible, as close as needed", by

pseudonymisation/anonymisation of personal data where possible and by agreeing on a limited embargo. Data transfer agreements may be initiated if required, for example to organisations in countries outside of the participating study sites.

- Data ownership will remain with the country teams in which the data was collected.
- All data will be stored in accordance with GDPR legislation and recognised data security standards. Identifiable data will be securely stored for two years after research findings are published, or for six years if the findings are not published, and then destroyed. De-identified data may be stored for longer.
- All digital data, including audio recordings, transcriptions, and any digital documents, will be permanently deleted using a reputable data erasure software which will overwrite the data multiple times to ensure it is irrecoverable.
- If any data is stored in encrypted form, it will be decrypted using appropriate encryption keys before deletion to ensure it is effectively destroyed.
- Any physical documents, notes, or printed materials containing identifiable data will be shredded using cross-cut shredders to render them unreadable.

All data will be managed in the first instance by each country partner. Each site will anonymise and clean data to ensure the confidentiality of the participants and data quality. Each site will use the data for their in-country analysis. Participant consent for sharing of anonymised outputs with project partners will be sought as part of the informed consent process. Participants will also be asked to consent for further follow-up and for us to keep their contact details securely on our secure server for the duration of the project.

All partners will have equal responsibility for meeting data standards and legal requirements in the context of the work they undertake in the project.

Concerning risk management and legal compliance, all participants to the project must be aware of their obligations as potential data processors (where appropriate) as well as issues beyond data and information protection and privacy described above. Actions should be taken to ensure that those handling subjects identifiable or sensitive information are made fully aware of their responsibilities and obligations to respect confidentiality in compliance with market standards (e.g.: ISO/IEC 27001:2005), best practices and legal requirements under the GDPR. Our research will comply with EU and national data protection law. HIGH Horizons will address the overall legal framework that is stated in the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation 2016/679) on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (GDPR). Also, it will consider the relevant procedures for protecting citizens' rights as reported by EGE and as proclaimed in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000/C 364/01). In addition to the more general and EU wide guidelines, partners will adhere to and respect national regulations and laws. All partners are aware of their responsibilities in that sense and will follow the established rules.

8.2 Sample size

Given our primary objective of assessing the feasibility and usability, no formal sample size calculation has been performed. However, for each of the three study sites with 200 women (and their children) enrolled and a conservative population proportion of the quantitative outcome (e.g., acceptability) and 95% confidence level, we will have a nearly 7% margin of error around the sample proportion estimate. This will provide relevant information to inform future policy and practice.

Additionally, each site will enrol 20 health workers (total 60 health workers) from selected health facilities in the three countries. Similar to above, no formal sample size has been conducted and it is expected that the qualitative inquiries will

generate detailed and in-depth understanding of the feasibility and usability of the ClimApp-MCH, and that data saturation will be achieved.

In relation to our secondary effectiveness objective, the 200 pregnant and postpartum women recruited in each country will allow us, with 95% confidence and 80% power, to show a 10% increase in the proportion of women reporting adequate knowledge, assuming that 50% of women have adequate knowledge at baseline.

8.3 Quantitative data analysis

Data collected through the ClimApp-MCH and the semi-structured questionnaires will be consolidated and summed up in contingency tables, separated into thematic areas such as sections on usability, acceptability and uptake, heat exposure and health responses.

For usability, user satisfaction, uptake of the ClimApp-MCH, the data will be analysed using descriptive statistics such as satisfaction rate, frequency of the use of EWS, and SUS interpretation method.

For knowledge gain and preventive action taken based on the messages and recommendations of the ClimApp-MCH, the data will be compared between pre and post implementation of ClimApp-MCH, in order to see if there is an increased knowledge, awareness and understanding of heat stress and related health risks, and behaviour changes (actions taken as recommended by the EWS). When there are sufficient users' responses while using the app over a period, a dose-response i.e. whether the more the participants use the app, the more knowledge gained will be analysed. This would strengthen our understanding of the effectiveness of the app.

Statistical tests of the differences between pre and post EWS implementation, and across countries will be conducted including T-test, Chi-square test, etc. The changes of knowledge gain, uptake of the EWS over time since the enrolment,

following up until the end point will also be analysed using for example ANOVA, multivariate analyses when several factors that may affect the changes are considered. The acceptance of the messages within each country, between countries and combined will be evaluated based on descriptive statistics and the Chi-square test.

8.4 Qualitative data analysis

Focus group discussion and / or in-depth interview recordings will be transcribed verbatim, and translated to English, for analysis. Quality checks on the transcriptions will be carried out by the research team, where a sample of transcripts will be spot-checked against the audio to ensure fidelity of transcription. If a substantial portion (i.e., more than 30%) of a transcript has been translated into English, this translation will be checked through back-translation into the original language and then reviewed by a native speaker of this language.

The qualitative data analysis will be performed with directed content analysis² with activity theory as a guiding theoretical framework¹. The interviews will be coded using qualitative data management software (like NVivo) using a priori coding tree to which additional codes are added through emerging themes from fieldwork and analysis. A thematic analysis will be conducted to answer research questions. The free text answers will provide insights into the cohesion of important terms related to heat stress and usability of the EWS.

8.5 Cost-consequence analysis of EWS

We will undertake a cost consequence analysis of the adaptation and distribution of the ClimApp-MCH for use in pregnant women in Sweden, Zimbabwe and South Africa. A combination of top-down and ingredient-based costing approaches will be used to generate cost estimates for ClimApp-MCH. All costing will be estimated from the provider's and household perspectives, and financial and economic costs will be calculated for all inputs e.g. data generation and analysis; programming of

the app; message generation, including Photovoice and production of infographics; and app distribution. The consequences will be estimated in terms of app utilization, health service utilization, and a reduction in heat stress, improvement of wellbeing and any other health or wellbeing outcomes that are identified during evaluation of the app.

The results will cover the costs of setting up and running the EWS, describe the distribution of costs across intervention components, the unit cost per woman reached by the EWS, and the cost consequence analysis.

9 Ethical considerations

9.1 Review boards

All participating sites will obtain approval from relevant local ethics committees. Before the study commences, the country Principal Investigator will ensure that the study protocol, participant information sheet, informed consent forms, and any other supporting documentation have been approved by the appropriate research ethics committee that is responsible for the study site.

Each site will prepare a site-specific protocol and secure local ethical clearance, specifically obtained from:

- LSHTM ethics committee in the UK
- National Ethical Review Board in Sweden
- Human Research Ethics Committee of the University of the Witwatersrand in South Africa
- Medical Research Council in Zimbabwe
- Research Council of Zimbabwe.

9.2 Informed consent

Before each participant is enrolled into the study, informed consent will be obtained in accordance with local and international ethical guidelines. The participant will be given a copy of the informed consent form, a copy of which will be retained by the research team. The informed consent form will be attached to a participant information sheet that will provide further information about the study, with an emphasis on voluntary participation. Participants can decline participation in the study without disadvantages or repercussions. They can also withdraw their consent for study participation at any time.

9.3 Anonymity, confidentiality and safety

A file linking names and unique identification number will be kept electronically using encryption and password protection and be accessible only to study staff. No information that has personal identifiers will be shared with any external partners.

The study results will be published for scientific purposes, but anonymity will be protected at all times, and we will ensure that as far as possible, no results can be linked to specific individuals. The participants will be informed that the usability survey and interview will be transcribed and analysed. The free texts submitted in the survey could be used as material for analysis similar to transcription and suitable quotes could be used in manuscript. The texts will not be linked to any individual participant.

9.4 Risks

This evaluation of the heat-health early warning system ClimApp-MCH, a mobile phone app, poses minimal risks to participants.

Each country site will implement a distress protocol, clearly outlining the procedures to be followed in cases where a participant becomes unwell or experiences distress during the course of the study.

9.5 Benefits

The participants have the opportunity to install and use a free heat-health early warning app, and get notified when facing impending heat risks. The app will provide relevant recommendations to take protective actions to reduce potential risks.

9.6 Monetary/other reimbursements

Participants will not incur any costs for participating in this study. Monetary or other reimbursement will be provided according to the guidelines in each country.

10 Dissemination

The results of this study will be published in scientific journals, presented in international conferences and communicated through the project website, social media, and by all our partners, including WHO. WP6 focuses on dissemination and communication.

11 Timeline

The timing of data collection in each country is contingent on seasonal variations, with a primary focus on scheduling most follow-ups during the warmer months of the respective countries.

Figure 1. Gantt Chart of the study timeline in each of the three countries

Project years	2024												2025												2026			
Months	Jan	Feb	March	April	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	March	April	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	March	April
Project months	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	43	44
South Africa	Visit 1: Enrolment						Visit 2: Follow-up interview: focus group						Visit 3: Close-out						D 5.3									
							data						data															
Zimbabwe	Visit 1: Enrolment						Visit 2: Follow-up interview: focus group						Visit 3: Close-out						D 5.3									
							data						data															
Sweden							Visit 1: Enrolment						Visit 2: Follow-up interview: focus group						D 5.3									
							data						data															

12 References

Burkart KG, Brauer M, Aravkin AY, Godwin WW, Hay SI, He J, et al. Estimating the cause-specific relative risks of non-optimal temperature on daily mortality: a two-part modelling approach applied to the Global Burden of Disease Study. *Lancet* 2021; 398(10301):685-697.

Copernicus, 2024. 2023 is the hottest year on record, with global temperatures close to the 1.5°C limit. [Online]. Available: <https://climate.copernicus.eu/copernicus-2023-hottest-year-record>

Eggeling J, Rydenfält C, Kingma B, Toftum J, Gao C. The usability of ClimApp: A personalized thermal stress warning tool. *Climate Services*. 2022;27:100310.

Folkerts MA, Boshuizen AW, Gosselink G, Gerrett N, Daanen HAM, Gao C, Toftum J, Nybo L, Kingma BRM. 2021. Predicted and user perceived heat strain using the ClimApp mobile tool for individualized alert and advice. *Climate Risk Management*, 34 (2021), 100381.

Hsieh H-F, Shannon SE. Three approaches to qualitative content analysis. *Qualitative health research*. 2005;15(9):1277-88.

ISO 9241-11:2018(en), Ergonomics of human-system interaction — Part 11: Usability: Definitions and concepts, <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:9241:-11:ed-2:v1:en>

NIOSH. 2016. NIOSH criteria for a recommended standard: occupational exposure to heat and hot environments. By Jacklitsch B, Williams WJ, Musolin K, Coca A, Kim J-H, Turner N. Cincinnati, OH: U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health, DHHS (NIOSH) Publication 2016-106. Criteria for a Recommended Standard: Occupational Exposure to Heat and Hot Environments (cdc.gov)

SUS: A Quick and Dirty Usability Scale by John Brooke (read full text or download as a PDF, and download the proper citation)

WMO 2024. 2023 State of Climate Services – Health and IPCC Working Group II – Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Fact sheet – Health: Climate Change Impacts and Risks. 2023

WMO/WHO and GHHIN, 2022. From the G7 Health Communiqué to Action: Health and Climate - Heat Preparedness through Early Warning Systems. G7, Germany.

WMO/WHO, 2015. Heatwaves and Health: Guidance on Warning-System Development. WMO-No. 1142.

13 Annexes

13.1 Annex I: ClimApp-MCH usability survey

The ClimApp-MCH draft usability survey questions:

➤ **Baseline questions**

This survey sets the baseline values before the training and use of the ClimApp-MCH.

1. Do you have experience of using mobile phone and app: yes/no
2. Your location and country?
3. What is your age (in years)?
4. When is your due date?
5. What is your occupation/employment and years of education?
6. Are your professional and personal daily physical activities at a high, moderate or low level?
7. Did you suffer from heat related illnesses before?
8. What is your gestational age? How many children do you have? Any other obstetric history (and pregnancy related information if applicable)?
9. Child health information and nurturing behaviors, e.g. breastfeeding (for postpartum women only)
10. Knowledge and behaviour related to heat impacts on health (what you know/understand about heat-health risks and how you would reduce potential heat risks before the EWS implementation based on the case describing heat stress risks in Annex II.)
11. Have you experienced any extreme heat that made your daily household activities and/or work very difficult to perform? If yes, how many days?

For health workers we will additionally ask the following:

1. Have you ever had your work performance seriously impacted by heat stress?
2. If you encountered serious heat related health problems, what were the symptoms?
3. Have you ever felt mentally unwell due to extreme heat conditions?
4. Were you able to reduce the heat stress?
5. What measures did you use to avoid heat stress?
6. Have you participated in taking care of a child delivery that was seriously impacted by heat?
7. If yes, were there any complications of the pregnant/postpartum women? What are the complications?

8. During childbirth in hot seasons, are you able to make sure that the pregnant woman is drinking sufficient fluids?

➤ **Follow-up (month 2) questions**

This survey will evaluate the usability and acceptance of the ClimApp-MCH based on System Usability Scale. It will also include questions regarding heat related experiences regarding the delivery and the postpartum period, solemnly focusing on heat stress.

1. SUS or PSSUQ Likert scale
2. Did the heat impact childbirth?
3. Were there any complications directly related to heat?
4. Has your child shown any signs of heat related illnesses? if yes, what were the signs?
5. Knowledge and behaviour related to heat impacts on health (what you know/understand about heat-health risks and how you would reduce potential heat risks after the EWS implementation based on the case describing heat stress risks in Annex II.)

➤ **Final endline (month 6) questions**

This survey will evaluate the usability and acceptance of the ClimApp-MCH based on System Usability Scale. The survey will also ask the participants to specify how they would reduce potential heat stress by behavioural measures based on the EWS advice/messages and a case describing risks with heat stress (Annex II). The survey will also ask questions about their general understanding of heat-health risks.

1. System Usability Scale (SUS) or Post-Study System Usability Questionnaire (PSSUQ) Likert scale
2. Were the EWS messages clearly formulated? And could you easily understand?
3. Did you feel that the messages were relevant for you?
4. Did the messages make you change your behaviour so that you were prepared for a hot day?
5. How would you reduce potential heat risks based on the case describing heat stress risks in Annex II)?

6. Do you believe that the EWS assisted you in estimating and warning heat risks in a way that reflects your actual heat stress experience?
7. Which aspects of the ClimApp-MCH did you find particularly useful / insightful?
8. Any other comments and suggestions.

➤ **System Usability Scale (SUS)**

When a System Usability Scale is used, participants are asked to score the following 10 items on a 5-point Likert agreement scale with one of five responses that range from Strongly disagree to Strongly agree:

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1	2	3	4	5

1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently.
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex.
3. I thought the system was easy to use.
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use.
9. I felt very confident using the system.
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

The SUS survey is available at the following website including information on how to evaluate the survey results:

<https://www.usability.gov/how-to-and-tools/methods/system-usability-scale.html>

➤ **Post-Study System Usability Questionnaire (PSSUQ)**

(the 1st and 16th questions are related to acceptance and satisfaction)

PSSUQ Version 3 consists of 16 questions with 7 options (+ NA option) to choose from. It is widely used to measure users' perceived satisfaction of a website,

software, system or product at the end of a study (<https://uiuxtrend.com/pssuq-post-study-system-usability-questionnaire/>).

On a scale between Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree, users rate the following statements:

1. Overall, I am satisfied with how easy it is to use this system.
2. It was simple to use this system.
3. I was able to complete the tasks and scenarios quickly using this system.
4. I felt comfortable using this system.
5. It was easy to learn to use this system.
6. I believe I could become productive quickly using this system.
7. The system gave error messages that clearly told me how to fix problems.
8. Whenever I made a mistake using the system, I could recover easily and quickly.
9. The information (such as online help, on-screen messages, and other documentation) provided with this system was clear.
10. It was easy to find the information I needed.
11. The information was effective in helping me complete the tasks and scenarios.
12. The organization of information on the system screens was clear.
13. The interface of this system was pleasant.
14. I liked using the interface of this system.
15. This system has all the functions and capabilities I expect it to have.
16. Overall, I am satisfied with this system.

Before rating the usability scales above, the participant should perform two to three specific tasks related to the EWS functionalities. For example, ask the participant to 1) find out where the heat risk warning is presented in the app? 2) where are the advice messages given? 3) submit participant's perceived heat stress to the app data server through the app?

13.2 Annex II: Knowledge on heat-health risks assessment

The knowledge increase will be evaluated and compared between pre and post EWS implementation, based on

1. the understanding of heat-health risks,
2. the advice/messages they have followed (actions taken), and
3. the response to the case below where the participants are allowed to freely describe behavioural measures to reduce the risks of heat.

Case of heat stress:

“Imagine that you’ve heard that tomorrow will be a very hot day. You feel today is already quite hot, and you sweat while performing an everyday activity outdoors. Tomorrow you are going to do the same activity but for an even longer duration. How are you going to prepare to avoid heat related health risks?”

The expected measures are:

1. Reduce physical work/exercise intensity.
2. Reschedule activity to cooler periods of the day.
3. Move activity to shaded areas, avoid solar radiation.
4. Take more breaks.
5. Drink sufficient water before, during and after heat exposure. Avoid body dehydration. Check urine colour. The colour should be light.
6. Reduce clothing insulation and evaporative resistance, wear clothing that does not absorb solar heat.
7. Wear shading hat to reduce solar radiation onto the face, head and body.
8. Increase area of exposed skin (if solar radiation is not too high) to increase heat dissipation and sweat evaporation.
9. Increase ventilation, for example use fans, stay in ventilated areas.
10. Avoid working and staying in humid areas.
11. Seek cooler areas, for example use green energy powered air conditioning.
12. Perform activity in a group to reduce risks of fainting/dizziness in the heat.

13.3 Annex III: Focus group discussion topic guide

Questions will be adapted according to each country's context and sample.

Introduction

- Icebreaker
- Opening questions about perceptions of heat on their pregnancies/post-partum lives (women) and their jobs (HWs)

Usability of the EWS

- Can you tell me about your experience using the EWS?
- How was it to start using the EWS?
- Did you ever feel lost?
- Were there any problems with finding the function or information that you wanted?
- Was it difficult to change your individual input into the app, such as age?
- Was there anything that did not function as you imagined it would?

Messaging

- Have you learned anything new from using the app? What?
- What did you think about the warning and messages/advice presented to you in the EWS? (Prompts: Were they vague or clear?)
- Were the messages appropriate for your circumstances? How so or why not?
- Which messages did you receive that you remember now? Why do you remember those?
- What would you like to change with the EWS?
- What was the best feature or features of the EWS?
- Is there anything else you would like to add before we finish this interview?
- Show a selection of messages and icons that were broadcast through the EWS and ask about their interpretation, meaning, and potential for improvement, one by one

Productivity

- Was your productivity affected by EWS?
- How did heat affect your productivity?